

POLITICAL CHANGES AND EDUCATIONAL REFORMS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article contains information about the reforms implemented in our country regarding the foreign language and the requirements for its popularization.

Key words: foreign language, English language, reforms, higher education institutions, certificates, demand, opportunities.

After our country gained independence, the demand and interest in learning and teaching foreign languages increased, and many opportunities are being created for young people in this regard. It can be said that improving the quality of education, developing the teaching of foreign languages, improving the knowledge, skills and abilities of young people in learning different languages has become one of the priority tasks of our state's policy in the field of education. The current leader of our country, Sh. Mirziyoyev, has given important instructions for the implementation of measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages initiated by the first President, and has not neglected to ensure its implementation. In our republic, new methods and requirements for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers have been developed in accordance with European requirements.

Within the framework of the program, textbooks, educational literature, manuals were created for students of educational institutions of our republic. In addition, in accordance with these requirements, the training rooms were equipped with modern information and communication techniques and equipment. As a result of this attention, the demand for learning foreign languages is increasing day by day. Certain tasks are also required of science experts and students. The pedagogues of higher education institutions were tasked with the task of further studying and teaching the language they have acquired, using the pedagogical experiences of developed countries abroad, and creating a modern, effective methodology of language teaching on this basis. Teaching foreign languages and The issue of developing educational programs based on modern methods and introducing them to all stages of the educational system is also becoming an important task in the agenda for evaluating the knowledge of young students.

According to the decision of the head of our state dated May 13, 2019 "On measures to implement national and international evaluation system certificates for admission to higher education institutions", tests will be held from the 2020-2021 academic year. language is also included, and the language level is set the same for all undergraduate courses. They are required to have B2 level from a number of national and international certificates such as IELTS (5.5), CEFR, IBS (72), Cambridge Assessment, English FCE, etc. In the last five years, the number of graduates with language certificates has increased for ten times.

On May 6, 2021, the head of our country Sh. Mirziyoyev, under the chairmanship of Mirziyoyev, a video meeting was held on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages. In our country, every year several areas of science are selected and developed with special attention.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said that the graduates of any educational institution up to the higher education institution in Uzbekistan must know at least two foreign languages. Now new employees hired in all government agencies are required to know at least one foreign language. This requirement also applies to employees of state agencies who want to be promoted to a higher position.

Uzbekistan's policy of openness is actively entering the world market, the expansion of international cooperation in all fields increases the need to know foreign languages. Today, in 25 higher educational institutions of our country, studies and teaching are conducted in foreign languages. In comparison, in 2016 there were only 7 of them.

Language exchange is extremely important for the exchange of cultures, for the development of societies, and for understanding other people and, in some sense, caring for peace and determining what is important for them.

Completing such a request and achieving the intended result, qualified representatives of the field are working hard on themselves and contributing to the popularization of foreign languages in our country. The most gratifying thing is that employees who receive 50% extra pay for their work are encouraged, and their families are enjoying prosperity.

In conclusion, it can be said that using all the necessary opportunities and achieving many goals in one's field requires only hard work. In order not to make mistakes and face problems in the process of learning foreign languages, it is necessary to take a responsible approach to mastering it and work on it regularly. Only then can high results be achieved. Any person who wants to have a place in society should first of all know his mother tongue, and a person who wants to achieve success in the world community should definitely know foreign languages. Since learning several languages is becoming a necessity in our country, it is the responsibility of every specialist to perform this task in the future.

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